

Reduction of Information Systems via Rough Set Model

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Abstract

Rough sets are efficient for attribute reduction and in extracting rules in data mining. There are many important problems in rough sets and we use algorithms to solve them. An important idea of rough sets is to approximately represent a whole space with a certain subspace. We can use lower and upper operators largely to determine the approximation accuracy. We also study graph representations of lower and upper approximations. This paper will illustrate a medical application by sing right neighborhood and initial neighborhood then core initial neighborhood will be computed.

Keywords: Approximate reasoning; indiscernibility lower and upper approximations; rough sets; boundary regions; rough membership function; decision rules dependencies to a degree.

1. Introduction

Rough set theory proposed by Pawlak is an efficient tool for data processing in many practical problems. In these years Rough Set has attracted research interest. Rough set has been widely used in feature selection and knowledge discovery. A rapid growth at interest in rough set applications can be seen lately in the number of international workshops, conferences and seminars are directly dedicated to rough sets include this approach to solve such problems. A large number of research papers on various aspect of rough sets and their applications have been published in recent years as a result of this attention. The theory has been followed by several software Systems. Rough sets are applied in many domains such as medicine, finance, telecommunication, vibration systems, image analysis pattern recognition, control theory, conflict resolution, intelligent agents, process industry and marketing, the reader is referred to [1, 10, 22] for the notions used in this survey article.

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There are several research in Rough Set theory and graph theory handled medical applications with new definitions. We will mention some of them by the way of counting and not limiting. One can use this applications by some programs on computers to diagnose some diseases for example, El-Sayed et al. [8] mentioned the disease of (Covid-19) to illustrate the significance of deciding the impact factors for (Covid-19) infection, this application was based on a reflexive relation although Pawlak's rough set and some of its generalizations couldn't be applied to solve such this problems but they could success in solving this problem using the suggested technique with algorithm.

Al-shami [1,2,3] successfully applied new types of rough neighborhoods to classify the patients according to the level of infection. El-Bably and El-Atik [10] holed the disease of corona virus on set β -rough sets approximations and soft β -rough topologies.

El-Atike and Wahba [6] made research about a new model of a blood circulation system of the human heart based on blood paths on topological separation axioms with vertices and edges of the heart model. El-Atik and Hassan [7] wrote paper that discussed some models for medicine which will give a solution for some real-life problems. This application was for flu disease, and they showed this problem via rough set and graph theories. Also they showed another example about "the fetal circulation" with nano topology, graph and $NI\alpha$ -open set on the blood circulation in the Fetus. Nasef et al. [18] made another idea about Congenital Anomaly through approximate reasoning and Rough membership function, in this paper Nasef et al. talked about O-micron virus and discussed the reduction of attributes and decision rules. Nasef et al. [19] talked about a medical application called urinary system with a digraph theory and nano topology, described the flow rate of filtered fluid through the kidney with graph model.

Hassanien and Ali [2] wrote about classification rules of Breast Cancer Data from fine needle aspirates from human breast tissue. They have collected data by Dr. W. Wolberg at the Wisconsin University.

Zhang [23] wrote about the selection of mist informative genes from huge noise for Cancer classification and construction of direct gene regulatory networks at different levels, this paper as new insights with α -depended degree and gene expression profiling. Meenachi et al. [15] mentioned diagnosing Cancer disease using fuzzy rough set theory with feature selection instance selection, classification and performance analysis. Particle swarm optimization techniques used for feature selection Phrase so on look [15, 16, 17, 18].

This paper introduces basic notions and will illustrate them with simple examples.

2. Rough sets

Rough set theory deals with the classificatory analysis of data tables. This data can be acquired from human experts and it must be discrete. Today, there exist methods that allow processing with continuous values. The main idea of this analysis is to synthesize approximation of some concepts. From the acquired data. An important feature of rough set is that it is followed by practical implementations that support interactive model development such that software systems in elevators that implement rough set methods as we will see next.

2.1. Information systems

They are tables where each row represents a case, an event, a patient or an object. Every column represents an attribute (a variable, an observation, a property, etc.) that can be measured for each object. This table is called an information system, it is a pair $A = (U, A)$ where (U) is non-empty finite set of object called universe, and (A) is a non-empty finite set of attribute such that $a : U \rightarrow V_a$ for every $a \in A$, V_a is called the value set of a .

2.2. Indiscernibility

A decision system expresses all the knowledge about the model. This table may be unnecessarily large in part as it is redundant in at least two ways. The same objects may be represent several times or some of attributes may be superfluous. A binary relation $R \subseteq X \times X$ which is reflexive (i. e., an object is in relation with itself $x R x$), symmetric (if $x R y$ then $y R x$) and transitive (if $x R y$ and $y R z$ then $x R z$) is called an equivalence relation.

The equivalence class of (x) as an element such that $x \in X$ consists of all objects $y \in X$ thus $x R y$.

Let $A = (U, A)$ be an information system, then any $B \subseteq A \ni \text{IND}_A(B)$

$$\text{IND}_A(B) = \{(x, x^-) \in U^2 / \forall a \in B a(x) = a(x^-)\},$$

and it is called B -indiscernibility relation. If $(x, x^-) \in \text{IND}_A(B)$ then objects x, x^- are indiscernible from each other by attributes from B , $[x]_B$ is called the equivalence class if $B \rightarrow \text{IND}_A(B)$.

We can omit the subscript A in the indiscernibility relation if it is clear which system we meant.

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2.3. Set Approximations

An equivalence relation induces a partitioning of the universe $(U) \rightarrow$ (the set of cases) those partitions can be used to build new subsets of (U) .

Let $A = (U, R)$ be an information system and $X \subseteq U$, we can approximate X using only the information contained in B . By B -lower and B -upper approximations of X denoted $\underline{\text{apr}}(X)$, $\overline{\text{apr}}(X)$ where:

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{x \in X \mid [x]_R \subseteq X\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{x \in X \mid [x]_R \cap X \neq \emptyset\},$$

and objects in $\underline{\text{apr}}(X)$ can be classified with certainty as members of X of knowledge in B . While $\overline{\text{apr}}(X)$ can be classified as possible members of X of knowledge in B .

There exist a subset of members that we can't decisively classify into X of knowledge in B called the B -boundary region of X . The set $\text{BN}_B(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X)$ while $U - \overline{\text{apr}}(X)$ is called B -outside region of X which consist of objects that can be classified as don't belong to X .

If the boundary region is not empty the set is called rough set. But if it is empty such that $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \emptyset$, the set is called "crisp set".

Example 1: Let $W = \{x \mid \text{walk}(x) = \text{Yes}\}$ and $\underline{\text{apr}}(W) = \{x_1, x_6\}$, $\overline{\text{apr}}(W) = \{x_1, x_3, x_4, x_6\}$ and $\text{BND}_A(W) = \{x_3, x_4\}$ and $U - \overline{\text{apr}}(W) = \{x_2, x_5, x_7\}$. Then walk is rough as the boundary region is not empty, this is shown in Fig. 1. It is seemed easily that the lower is the interior and the upper is the closure in the topology generate by the indiscernibility relation.

Here, one can define the following four basic notions of rough sets,

- a) X is roughly definable, iff $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) \neq \emptyset$ and $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) \neq U$.
- b) X is totally undefinable, iff $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \emptyset$ and $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = U$.

Fig. 1.

c) X is externally undefinable, iff $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) \neq \phi$ and $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = U$.

d) X is internally undefinable, iff $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \phi$ and $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) \neq U$.

Here some important relations in classical rough set theory:

- (1) $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) \subseteq X \subseteq \overline{\text{apr}}(X)$.
- (2) $\underline{\text{apr}}(\phi) = \overline{\text{apr}}(\phi) = \phi$, and $\underline{\text{apr}}(U) = \overline{\text{apr}}(U) = U$.
- (3) $\overline{\text{apr}}(X \cup Y) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) \cup \overline{\text{apr}}(Y)$.
- (4) $\underline{\text{apr}}(X \cap Y) = \underline{\text{apr}}(X) \cap \underline{\text{apr}}(Y)$.
- (5) $X \subseteq Y$ implies $\underline{\text{apr}}(X) \subseteq \underline{\text{apr}}(Y)$, and $\overline{\text{apr}}(X) \subseteq \overline{\text{apr}}(Y)$.
- (6) $\underline{\text{apr}}(X \cup Y) \supseteq \underline{\text{apr}}(X) \cup \underline{\text{apr}}(Y)$.
- (7) $\overline{\text{apr}}(X \cap Y) \subseteq \overline{\text{apr}}(X) \cap \overline{\text{apr}}(Y)$.
- (8) $\underline{\text{apr}}(-X) = -\overline{\text{apr}}(X)$.
- (9) $\overline{\text{apr}}(-X) = -\underline{\text{apr}}(X)$.
- (10) $\underline{\text{apr}}(\underline{\text{apr}}(X)) = \overline{\text{apr}}(\underline{\text{apr}}(X)) = \underline{\text{apr}}(X)$.
- (11) $\overline{\text{apr}}(\overline{\text{apr}}(X)) = \underline{\text{apr}}(\overline{\text{apr}}(X)) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X)$,

where $-X$ denotes $(U - X)$.

Rough set can be also characterized numerically by the following

$$\alpha_B(X) = \frac{|\underline{\text{apr}}(X)|}{|\overline{\text{apr}}(X)|},$$

which is called: the accuracy of approximation, where $|X|$ denotes the cardinality of $X \neq \phi$ obviously $0 \leq \alpha_B(X) \leq 1$.

If $\alpha_B(X) = 1$, X is crisp with respect to B (X is precise with respect to B).

If $\alpha_B(X) < 1$, X is rough with respect to B (X is vague with respect to B).

2.4. Reducts

In the previous section we used one natural dimension of reducing data which is to identify equivalence classes (objects that are indiscernible using the available attributes).

The other dimension in reduction is to keep only those attributes that preserve the indiscernibility relation and set approximation. The rejected attributes are redundant. Since their removal cannot worsen the classification.

Definition 4.2.1. There are several such subsets of attributes and those are minimal in cardinality of attributes. One

can show that $\binom{m}{\lfloor m/2 \rfloor}$ is a relation that shows the number of reducts of an information system.

This means that when we compute reducts it is a non-trivial task that can't be solved by a simple increase of computational resources. It is one of the bottlenecks of the rough set methodology.

Fortunately, there are heuristic based on genetic algorithms that compute many reducts in acceptable time, unless the number of attributes is very high.

Given (U, A) and $B \subseteq A$ such that $IND(B) = IND(A)$. Thus, A_{reduct} is a minimal set of attributes from A that makes the ability to perform classifications as the whole attribute set A and preserves the partitioning of the universe.

2.5. Rough membership

In the case of rough sets, the notion of membership is a bit different from other sets. In classical set theory, membership function is the characteristic function for the set either an element belongs to or not, i. e., the function takes the value 1 and 0, but the rough membership function quantifies the degree of relative overlap between the set X and equivalence $[X]$ classes to which x belongs and it is defined as follows:

$$M_X^B : U \rightarrow [0, 1] \quad \text{and} \quad M_X^B(x) = \frac{|[x]_B \cap X|}{|[x]_B|},$$

with help of the definition above we can define the lower and upper approximations as follows:

by the use of arbitrary level of precision $\pi \in \left(\frac{1}{2}, 1\right]$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{x \mid M_X^B(x) \geq \pi\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{x \mid M_X^B(x) > 1 - \pi\}.$$

They obtained as a special case with $\pi = 1$.

Reduct

To express the idea of (reduct). Let $B \subseteq A$ and $a \in B$ in the knowledge system $I = (U, A)$ where $U \rightarrow$ universe, $A \rightarrow$ attributes, $R(B)$ is a binary relation

- a is dispensable in B if $R(B) = R(B - a)$, otherwise (a) is indispensable.
- The set B is independent if all its attributes are indispensable.
- $B^- \subseteq B$ is a reduct if B^- is an independent set and $R(B^-) = R(B)$.

We can call the attributes redundant if they are other than the reduct. Usually there are many reducts of the information system.

Core

Some attributes are redundant and the other are indispensable. The core is the set of attributes that are indispensable and it is the intersection between all reducts.

Let $Red(B)$ is the set of all reducts, $I = (U, A)$ where $B \subseteq A$ then the Core of B is $Core(B) = \bigcap Red(B)$.

So, Core is include in all reducts. thus, the Core is the most important subset of attributes.

Here are the algorithms, that shows the mechanism of rough set theory. It is written as a flow chart graph.

Flowchart 1. The machine of rough set theory.

Nowadays, the world interest in dealing with the new virus (SARS-COV-2) or (Covid-19). This virus came from China with a total number of patients each to 95171 person. It is the third highly pathogenic human virus that occurs in the last two decades after Corona virus and (SARS) [11]. Consequently, further spread in public through the person to person transmission and health care environments is crucial. It also transfer from dry surfaces, self inoculation of the nose, eye or mouth. A series of public social distancing measures to reduce rates of (Covid-19) were implemented in the context of the emergency response. In order to study and examine this dangerous virus, many researchers have published several papers.

Here our purpose in this work is to introduce a new method to make a topological reduction of the attributes of an information table. We can use a general binary relation to deal with the multi-information table (for example, a reflexive relation). So Pawlak's approach can't applied and hence we can't use Thivagar and Richard [10] method in this case, we can apply the method of generalized nano-topology in decision-making. We can also study the effect of

such a mathematical idea with continuous nature in exploration a real-life problem. In fact we present a medical application on corona virus disease (CoviD-19). Thus, we can determine the impact factors in infection caused by (CoviD-19). Finally, we also give some important algorithms which we use in examination of 10 patients. Doctors may use these results to make the best decision. rough set here can discover the vagueness of the death and help in decision-making of these dangerous real-life problems as these serious problems need accurate decisions in diagnosis.

2. Pawlak's rough sets and generalized rough sets

2.1. Pawlak rough set theory

Definition 2.1.1. Suppose that there exists two sets called A, B and (R) is from $A \rightarrow B$ is a binary relation is defined as $A \times B$ that is the set of ordered pairs $(\theta, \omega) \in R$, where $\theta \in A, \omega \in B$. We denote that R can be from A to A then it is called a binary relation on A . The ordered pair (θ, ω) can be represented as $\theta R \omega$ we read it as ω is related to θ by R .

Definition 2.1.2. A binary relation R on A is said to be:

- 1- Reflexive: if for each $\theta \in A, \theta R \theta$.
- 2- Symmetric: if $\theta, \omega \in A$ and $\theta R \omega$ then $\omega R \theta$.
- 3- Transitive: if $\theta, \omega, \rho \in A, \theta R \omega$ and $\omega R \rho$ then $\theta R \rho$.
- 4- Serial: $\forall x \in U, \exists y \in U$ s. t. $x R y, R N(x) \neq \phi$.
- 5- Similarly or tolerance: if R is a reflexive and symmetric.
- 6- Pre-order or dominance: if R is a reflexive and transitive.
- 7- Equivalence: if R is reflexive, symmetric and transitive relation.

2.2. Yao's rough sets

Definition 2.2.1 [7]. If R is a binary relation on the universe U . Then, for each $\alpha \in U$ we propose its "right neighborhood" as:

$$R_r(\alpha) = \{\beta \in U, \alpha R \beta\}.$$

Definition 2.2.2 [7]. If R is a binary relation on U then the right-lower and right-upper approximation of $A \subseteq U$ are, respectively:

$$\underline{\text{apr}}_r(A) = \{\alpha \in U : R_r(\alpha) \subseteq A\},$$

and

$$\overline{\text{apr}}_r(A) = \{\alpha \in U : R_r(\alpha) \cap A \neq \phi\}.$$

We can also define the right positive and right negative regions and right boundary, positive ${}_r(A) = \underline{\text{apr}}_r(A)$, negative ${}_r(A) = U - \overline{\text{apr}}_r(A)$, $\text{Bnd}_r(A) = \overline{\text{apr}}_r(A) - \underline{\text{apr}}_r(A)$, $\alpha_r(A) = \frac{|\underline{\text{apr}}_r(A)|}{|\overline{\text{apr}}_r(A)|}$ is called right accuracy of approximations.

3. Generalized rough sets based on a new type of generalized neighborhoods

Here we suggest a new generalized rough sets approximations called "initial-approximation" based on a new neighborhood called "initial neighborhood". This neighborhood is established from a general binary relation with no restricted conditions on the application field. A new generalized rough set based on initial neighborhood. Satisfy on properties of Pawlak's rough sets without any restrictions.

3.1. Initial neighborhood and properties

This concept is generated from a general binary relation.

Definition 3.1. [3] Consider R is a binary relation on U for $\alpha \in U$, we define its initial right neighborhood as:

$R_i(\alpha) = \{\beta \in U : R_r(\alpha) \subseteq R_r(\beta)\}$ with elementary properties as follow:

- (i) $\alpha \in R_i(\alpha)$.
- (ii) $R_i(\alpha) \neq \phi$.
- (iii) If $\beta \in R_i(\alpha)$, then $R_i(\beta) \subseteq R_i(\alpha)$.

Example 3.1. Consider $U = \{a, b, c, d\}$ and $R = \{(a, a), (b, a), (a, d), (c, d)\}$ is binary relation on U , then:

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} R_r(a) = \{a, d\}, \\ R_r(b) = \{a\}, \\ R_r(c) = \{d\}, \\ R_r(d) = \phi \end{array} \right\} \Rightarrow \left\{ \begin{array}{l} R_i(a) = \{a\}, \\ R_i(b) = \{a, b\}, \\ R_i(c) = \{a, c\}, \\ R_i(d) = U. \end{array} \right.$$

Clearly: $a \in R_i(b)$ and $R_i(a) \neq R_i(b)$. So in general, the right neighborhood and initial neighborhood are independent (not comparable) in case of R is reflexive, symmetric and transitive as illustrated in the previous example.

4. A Medical application via a nano-topology in decision-making of (CoviD-19)

The fast diffusion of (Covid-19) epidemic has caused widespread societal, economic and political disruption. It can be spread through physical contact between persons. Unfortunately, no successful therapy exists at this time. Wearing masks, washing, sterilizing and social distancing are only preventive measures available beside using Alcohol.

So, to avoid the spread of this virus we need accurate decision to diagnose the infection. This work is so important as it demonstrate the significance of our approach in optioning accurate tools to identify deciding factors of infection in humans. Here in the next application, we will use a binary relation to illustrate the significance of the suggested technique in decision-making. So the other methods like (Pawlak, Thivagar and Richard, Yao, Allam et. al., and Dai et. al.,) can't be used here so we can say that our method extends the field of rough sets in applications. We present an accurate tool in our approach. Our approach depends on removing superfluous attributes from conditions to produce a successfully reduced set and formulate the Core set.

Nowadays, (Covid-19) become another one that is called "(-Micron B. 1.1.529)" as a mutated virus. This disease is either super rare or mutated. This virus is highly contagious so the spread of it become faster. We collected the last information from experts about this virus-new-and they showed that it has a lot of mutations that affect the behavior of the new dangerous virus. This mutation is less dangerous than delta mutation but the spread of it cause increasing in number of patients and they may die. This variant was discovered of first in Potsoana in November 9th 2021 and it carries 50 mutations as total as "world Health organization" said. Now I went to some big isolation hospitals to bring some important information about this variant and we know the symptoms. Here are 10 Patients as a sample from the hospital and the most symptoms are Abdomain Pain, Diarrhea, Difficulty breathing, brain hemorrhage or brain stroke, cerebral thrombosis or coma, heart attack, less of taste or smell Dry cough and Temperature.

Table 1 shows 10 patients with symptoms of "Omicron".

Table 1: The information decision data set.

Patients	Serious symptoms			Most common symptoms				Decision Omicron <i>D</i>
	<i>a</i> ₁	<i>a</i> ₂	<i>a</i> ₃	<i>a</i> ₄	<i>a</i> ₅	<i>a</i> ₆	<i>a</i> ₇	
<i>U</i>	Heart attack	Difficulty breathing	Loss of taste	Diarrhea	Brain stroke	Temperature	Dry Cough	
<i>P</i> ₁	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	Yes	No	Yes
<i>P</i> ₂	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes
<i>P</i> ₃	No	No	No	Yes	No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>P</i> ₄	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
<i>P</i> ₅	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	No
<i>P</i> ₆	No	Yes	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	No
<i>P</i> ₇	No	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes	No
<i>P</i> ₈	No	No	Yes	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
<i>P</i> ₉	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No	No	No	Yes
<i>P</i> ₁₀	No	Yes	No	No	No	Yes	Yes	Yes

According to the previous table, those 10 patients suffer from the new variant virus "Omicron" and there were serious symptoms such as heart attack, difficulty in breathing, loss of taste, Diarrhea, brain stroke, temperature and dry cough. There are also most common symptoms and according to this information, we can take our decision and the application can be described as follows:

The set of objects $U = \{P_1, P_2, P_3, \dots, P_{10}\}$ denotes 10 patients listed in Table 1.

The symptoms that represent the attributes are $A = \{a_1, a_2, a_3, \dots, a_7\}$. Our approach is based on removing redundant attributes to produce the successfully reduced set and formulate the corset of attributes. I'd like to mention that the information obtained in this virus analysis is form 100 patients. Since the attributes in rows (objects) were identical 100 patients were reduced to 10 patients.

We are again drawing the consistent part of Table (1) by the next Table (2).

Table 2

U	A							Decision
	SS			MCS				
	<i>a</i> ₁	<i>a</i> ₂	<i>a</i> ₃	<i>a</i> ₄	<i>a</i> ₅	<i>a</i> ₆	<i>a</i> ₇	
<i>P</i> ₁	1	1	1	0	0	1	0	1
<i>P</i> ₂	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	1
<i>P</i> ₃	0	0	0	1	0	1	1	0

P_4	0	1	0	0	1	1	1	1
P_5	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	0
P_6	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0
P_7	0	0	0	0	1	1	1	0
P_8	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	0
P_9	1	1	1	1	0	0	0	1
P_{10}	0	1	0	0	0	1	1	1

From Table (2), we obtain the serious symptoms of every patient are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 V(P_1) &= \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_6\}, & V(P_2) &= \{a_2, a_5, a_6\}, \\
 V(P_3) &= \{a_4, a_6, a_7\}, & V(P_4) &= \{a_2, a_5, a_6, a_7\}, \\
 V(P_5) &= \{a_2, a_6, a_7\}, & V(P_6) &= \{a_2, a_5, a_6\}, \\
 V(P_7) &= \{a_5, a_6, a_7\}, & V(P_8) &= \{a_3, a_4, a_6\}, \\
 V(P_9) &= \{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}, & V(P_{10}) &= \{a_2, a_6, a_7\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

Now we can generate the following relation:

$$P_i R P_j \Leftrightarrow V(P_i) \subseteq V(P_j),$$

we can apply the previous relation in the table to include the neighborhoods of follows:

$$R = \{(P_1, P_1), (P_2, P_2), (P_2, P_4), (P_2, P_6), (P_3, P_3), (P_4, P_4), (P_5, P_5), (P_5, P_{10}), (P_6, P_6), (P_7, P_7), (P_8, P_8), (P_9, P_9), (P_{10}, P_{10})\}.$$

Thus the right neighborhoods of each element in U of the relation are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R_r(P_1) &= \{P_1\}, & R_r(P_2) &= \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \\
 R_r(P_3) &= \{P_3\}, & R_r(P_4) &= \{P_4\}, \\
 R_r(P_5) &= \{P_5, P_{10}\}, & R_r(P_6) &= \{P_6\}, \\
 R_r(P_7) &= \{P_7\}, & R_r(P_8) &= \{P_8\}, \\
 R_r(P_9) &= \{P_9\}, & R_r(P_{10}) &= \{P_{10}\}.
 \end{aligned}$$

We can generate 3 relations from the following:

If $P_i R P_j \Leftrightarrow V(P_i) \not\subseteq V(P_j)$, then we will deduce the right neighborhood relation as $R_r(P_i)$ then the initial neighborhood $R_i(P_i)$; $R_r(x) \subseteq R_r(y)$ after that core initial neighborhood as $R_i(P_i) = R_i(P_j)$.

From Table 2 we can make the following Table 3. Table 3 shows the general relation, right neighborhood relation, initial neighborhood relation and core initial relation

Table 3

P_i	$V(P_i)$	$R_V(P_i)$	$R_r(P_i)$	$R_i(P_i)$	$C \text{ int}(P_i)$
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P_1	$\{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_6\}$	$\{(P_1, P_2), (P_1, P_3), (P_1, P_4), (P_1, P_5), (P_1, P_6), (P_1, P_7), (P_1, P_8), (P_1, P_9), (P_1, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_1\}$	$\{P_1\}$
P_2	$\{a_2, a_5, a_6\}$	$\{(P_2, P_1), (P_2, P_3), (P_2, P_5), (P_2, P_7), (P_2, P_8), (P_2, P_9), (P_2, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_3, P_5, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_2, P_4, P_6\}$	$\{P_2, P_6\}$
P_3	$\{a_4, a_6, a_7\}$	$\{(P_3, P_1), (P_3, P_2), (P_3, P_4), (P_3, P_5), (P_3, P_6), (P_3, P_7), (P_3, P_8), (P_3, P_9), (P_3, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_3\}$	$\{P_3\}$
P_4	$\{a_2, a_5, a_6, a_7\}$	$\{(P_4, P_1), (P_4, P_2), (P_4, P_3), (P_4, P_5), (P_4, P_6), (P_4, P_7), (P_4, P_8), (P_4, P_9), (P_4, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_4, P_9\}$	$\{P_4\}$
P_5	$\{a_2, a_6, a_7\}$	$\{(P_5, P_1), (P_5, P_2), (P_5, P_3), (P_5, P_6), (P_5, P_7), (P_5, P_8), (P_5, P_9)\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_7, P_8, P_9\}$	$\{P_4, P_5, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_5\}$
P_6	$\{a_2, a_5, a_6\}$	$\{(P_6, P_1), (P_6, P_3), (P_6, P_5), (P_6, P_7), (P_6, P_8), (P_6, P_9), (P_6, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_3, P_5, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_2, P_4, P_6\}$	$\{P_6\}$
P_7	$\{a_5, a_6, a_7\}$	$\{(P_7, P_1), (P_7, P_2), (P_7, P_3), (P_7, P_5), (P_7, P_6), (P_7, P_8), (P_7, P_9), (P_7, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_5, P_6, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_4, P_7\}$	$\{P_7\}$

Table 3. Continue

P_i	$V(P_i)$	$R_V(P_i)$	$R_r(P_i)$	$R_i(P_i)$	$C \text{ int}(P_i)$
P_8	$\{a_3, a_4, a_6\}$	$\{(P_8, P_1), (P_8, P_2), (P_8, P_3), (P_8, P_4), (P_8, P_5), (P_8, P_6), (P_8, P_7), (P_8, P_9), (P_8, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_9, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_8\}$	$\{P_8\}$
P_9	$\{a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4\}$	$\{(P_9, P_1), (P_9, P_2), (P_9, P_3), (P_9, P_4), (P_9, P_5), (P_9, P_6), (P_9, P_7), (P_9, P_8), (P_9, P_{10})\}$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_{10}\}$	$\{P_9\}$	$\{P_9\}$

P_{10}	$\{a_2, a_6, a_7\}$	$\{(P_{10}, P_1), (P_{10}, P_2), (P_{10}, P_3),$	$\{P_1, P_2, P_3,$		
		$(P_{10}, P_6), (P_{10}, P_7), (P_{10}, P_8),$	$P_6, P_7, P_8,$	$\{P_{10}\}$	$\{P_{10}\}$
		$(P_{10}, P_9)\}$	$P_9\}$		

From table 3 we want to calculate the accuracy for 3 relations and choose the best

$$1- R_r = \{\{P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_3, P_5, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \\ \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_3, P_5, P_7, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \\ \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_5, P_6, P_8, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8, \\ P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_3, P_6, P_7, P_8, P_9\}\},$$

$$X = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \phi,$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = U,$$

$$\alpha_P(X) = \phi \rightarrow (\text{Not used}).$$

$$2- R_i(P_i) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_4, P_9\}, \{P_4, P_5, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \{P_4, P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}, \\ \{P_4, P_5, P_{10}\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_4, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\alpha_P(X) = \frac{|\underline{\text{apr}}(X)|}{|\overline{\text{apr}}(X)|} = \frac{3}{8} = 37.5\%.$$

$$3- R_C \text{int}(P_i) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_6\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_4\}, \{P_5\}, \{P_6\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}, \{P_{10}\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_4, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\alpha_P(X) = \frac{4}{6} = \frac{2}{3} = 66.666\%.$$

We choose the Core initial relation as it has the highest accuracy than the right neighborhood relation and initial neighborhood relation, for the relation

$$P_i R P_j \Leftrightarrow V(P_i) \not\subseteq V(P_j).$$

We also tray to use $P_i R P_j \Leftrightarrow V(P_i) \cap V(P_j) \neq \phi$.

Case 1: (Patients infected with (Omicron)).

The set of infected patients with "Omicron" is $X = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_9, P_{10}\}$. Then we get

$$U / \text{IND}_A(A) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_5, P_{10}\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}\},$$

and one can deduce that

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

and

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}.$$

Therefore, by using the nano topology and its basis of X, can deduce that:

$$\tau_A(X) = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\}\},$$

and

$$\beta_A(\tau_A(X)) = \{U, \underline{\text{apr}}(X), \text{Bnd}(X)\} = \{U, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\}.$$

Step 1: When the attribute a_1 "Heart attack" is removed:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_1) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_5, P_{10}\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\},$$

$$\tau(X) = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\},$$

$$\beta(\tau_{A-a_1}(X)) = \{U, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\}.$$

So $\beta(\tau_A(X)) = \beta\tau_{A-a_1}(X) \Rightarrow a_1 \notin \text{CORE}$.

Thus the attribute "Heart attack" is redundant or superfluous attribute.

Step 2: When the attribute a_2 "Difficulty breathing" is removed:

By the same manner as in Step 1 we get the neighborhoods as follows:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_2) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_4, P_6\}, \{P_5, P_{10}\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\},$$

$$\tau_{A-a_2}(X) = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_2, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\},$$

$$\beta(\tau_{A-a_2}(X)) = \{U, \{P_1, P_2, P_9\}, \{P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\}$$

that is $\beta(\tau_A(X)) \neq \beta\tau_{A-a_2}(X)$.

So the second attribute "Difficulty breathing" is dispensable. Thus we can't remove it from the table $\Rightarrow a_2 \in \text{CORE}(A)$.

Step 3: When we remove the attribute a_3 "Loss of Taste" from the table

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_3) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_9, P_{10}\},$$

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_{10}\}.$$

$$\tau_{A-a_3}(X) = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_{10}\}\},$$

$$\beta(\tau_{A-a_3}(X)) = \{U, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_{10}\}\}.$$

$$\beta(\tau_A(X)) \neq \beta(\tau_{A-a_3}(X)).$$

a_3 : "Loss of taste" is dispensible attribute, that is so we can't remove it.

Thus, "loss of taste" $a_3 \in \text{Core}(A)$.

Step 4: When we remove the attribute " Diarrhea" (a_4) from the table

We know from the previous that:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_4) = \{\{P_1\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_6\}, \{P_3\}, \{P_5, P_{10}\}, \{P_7\}, \{P_8\}, \{P_9\}\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_6, P_5, P_{10}, P_9\},$$

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}.$$

$$\beta(\tau_{A-a_4}(X)) = \{U, \underline{\text{apr}}(X), \text{Bnd}(X)\} = \{U, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{A-a_4}(X) = \{U, \phi, \underline{\text{apr}}(X), \overline{\text{apr}}(X), \text{Bnd}(X)\} = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\},$$

From this analysis we got an important information that is $\beta_A(\tau(X)) = \beta_{A-a_4}(\tau(X))$.

Thus the attribute (a_4) $\neq \text{CORE}(A)$ and it is a redundant attribute we can remove it from the table because it's unnecessary.

Step 5: When we remove (a_5) "Brain stroke" from the table:

Therefore, the symptoms of every patient are:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_5) = \{(P_1), (P_2, P_4, P_6), (P_3), (P_5, P_{10}), (P_7), (P_8), (P_9)\},$$

$$\underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_9\},$$

$$\overline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_6, P_5, P_{10}, P_9\},$$

$$\text{Bnd}(X) = \overline{\text{apr}}(X) - \underline{\text{apr}}(X) = \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}.$$

$$\beta(\tau_{A-a_5}(X)) = \{U, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\}.$$

$$\tau_{A-a_5}(X) = \{U, \phi, \{P_1, P_9\}, \{P_1, P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_9, P_{10}\}, \{P_2, P_4, P_5, P_6, P_{10}\}\},$$

Thus $\beta(\tau_A(X)) = \beta(\tau_{A-a_5}(X))$.

So, "Brain stroke" $a_5 \notin \text{CORE}(A)$.

We can remove (a_5) from the table because it is a redundant attribute.

Step 6: When we remove (a_6) "Temperature" from the table and make the following:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_6) = \{(P_1), (P_2, P_4, P_6), (P_3), (P_5, P_{10}), (P_7), (P_8), (P_9)\},$$

This relation is the same as the previous relation $(U / \text{IND}(A - a_5))$.

So, $a_6 \notin \text{CORE}(A)$.

The attribute "Temperature" is redundant.

Step 7: When we remove (a_7) "Dry cough" from the table and make the same analysis as presented we can know that:

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_7) = \{(P_1), (P_2, P_4, P_6), (P_3), (P_5, P_{10}), (P_7), (P_8), (P_9)\}.$$

So,

$$U / \text{IND}(A - a_7) = U / \text{IND}(A - a_6) = U / \text{IND}(A - a_5).$$

So, $a_7 \notin \text{CORE}(A)$.

It's a redundant attribute, we can remove it from the whole attributes.

Thus $\{a_2, a_3\} \in \text{CORE}(A)$.

So $\{\text{Difficulty breathing and Loss of taste}\}$ are so important in diagnosing Omicron disease by analysis of steps. We became sure of these steps from doctors also they ensure this by practicing with patients.

Case 2: (Patients are not infected with (Omicron)).

The set of non-infected patients with Omicron is $Y = \{P_3, P_5, P_6, P_7, P_8\}$. By making the same previous steps like as Case 1, we obtain the same results.

Observation: from the CORE, we observed that "loss of taste or smell and Difficulty breathing" are the key factors for (Covid-19) and (Omicron) and High Temperature is also key factor for (Covid-19) infection. Hence, these attributes are not dispensable attributes that represent the impact factors for (Omicron) infection.

5. Conclusion

The rough set approach to data analysis has many important advantages. Some of them are

- 1- Synthesis of efficient algorithms for finding hidden patterns in data.
- 2- Representation and processing of both qualitative and quantitative parameters and mixing of user defined and measured data.
- 3- Evaluation of significance data.
- 4- Synthesis of decision rules from data.
- 5- Interpretation of synthesized models.

Most algorithms are suited for parallel processing several theoretical and practical problems need further attention although rough set has many when we involve quantitative and qualitative attributes particularly, more research must be made here because comparison to other similar methods still requires. Last but not least, rough set computer is badly needed for more advanced applications some research is already in progress.

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